

tubes containing moist cotton to prevent wilting. The 10 first-instar nymphs were put into each test tube, and the top was fastened with muslin cloth. The percent of larval mortality was observed after 24 h.

The extract of Ptb33 significantly inhibited oviposition significantly compared with the control and other cultivars tested. Mortality rates were significantly higher for treatments using extracts of Ptb33, IET12008, and IR62 than for the other cultivars and controls tested.

The study revealed the differential reaction of rice accessions to *S. biformis*. ■

Adulterated pesticides in Cambodia

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Cambodia has recently emerged from 25 yr of war and political isolation during which the country's infrastructure and service networks were severely damaged or totally destroyed. During most of this period, agriculture existed in a state of low input/low output technology. A village-based communal system controlled production, and the central government provided farmers with subsidized farm inputs. Toward the end of the 1980s, fertilizer and pesticides were imported almost exclusively from the Soviet Union and farm produce sales were tightly controlled. As a result, subsidized inputs were scarce and the country was self-sufficient neither in rice nor vegetables.

At the beginning of the present decade, markets were opened and sales of farm inputs increased rapidly. Products were imported—often smuggled in—from a range of countries. No policy existed on the requisite quality or safety of the products and the government did not possess the necessary authority to implement any

regulatory programs. As a result, several dangerous chemicals banned in other countries were imported for sale in Cambodia.

A range of products is presently available in Phnom Penh and provincial markets, including organochlorine insecticides, organophosphorus products, carbamates, and pyrethroids. The cheapest and most popular pesticides were generally the most dangerous, classified in the WHO class I category. By 1995, use of these products was concentrated in vegetable areas close to the capital, Phnom Penh, and in intensive rice-growing areas near the Vietnam border.

Farmers observed that, despite the application of heavy doses of insecticides, pest kill was often low. Quality problems were suspected, so pesticide samples were collected from three markets within 15 km of Phnom Penh. Twenty-two products were analyzed by gas chromatography or liquid chromatography. Their active ingredients, their claimed strength, source, and measured concentration were determined (Table 1).

Analysis of 22 pesticide samples.

Active ingredient	Source	Claimed strength	FAO ^a tolerance	Measured strength	Concentration tolerance ^b
Carbaryl	Vietnam	-	-	49gkg ⁻¹	1
Fenitrothion	Japan	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	496 g L ⁻¹	1
Methamidophos	Vietnam	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	528 g L ⁻¹	1
Parathion methyl	Thailand	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	575 g L ⁻¹	1
Parathion methyl	Luxembourg	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	539 g L ⁻¹	1
Carbofuran	Vietnam	30 g kg ⁻¹	27- 33 g kg ⁻¹	26 g kg ⁻¹	2
DDT	Vietnam	-	-	78 g kg ⁻¹	2
Fenvalerate	Japan	200 g L ⁻¹	188-212 g L ⁻¹	186 g L ⁻¹	2
Methamidophos	Vietnam	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	470 g L ⁻¹	2
Methomyl	Thailand	900 g kg ⁻¹	875-925 g kg ⁻¹	828 g kg ⁻¹	2
Mevinphos	Thailand	240 g L ⁻¹	225-255 g L ⁻¹	217 g L ⁻¹	2
Dichlorvos	Thailand	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	266 g L ⁻¹	3
Mevinphos	Thailand	240 g L ⁻¹	225-255 g L ⁻¹	128 g L ⁻¹	3
Mevinphos	Thailand	240 g L ⁻¹	225-255 g L ⁻¹	131 g L ⁻¹	3
DDT	Vietnam	-	-	10.2g L ⁻¹	X
Dichlorvos	Vietnam	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	<0.5 g L ⁻¹	X
Dichlorvos	Gov't store	-	475-525 g L ⁻¹	73 g L ⁻¹	X
Endrin	Gov't store	-	-	<0.5 g L ⁻¹	X
Methamidophos	Vietnam	725 g L ⁻¹	700-750 g L ⁻¹	<5 g L ⁻¹	X
Monocrotophos	Vietnam	500 g L ⁻¹	475-525 g L ⁻¹	<5 g L ⁻¹	X
Monocrotophos	Gov't store	-	-	<5 g L ⁻¹	X
"Mosquito poison"	Khmer product	-	-	0	X

^a FAO, 1987. ^b 1 = within tolerable limits, 2 = below tolerable limits, 3 = well below tolerable limits. X = extremely low or nonexistent active ingredients.

Of the 22 samples analyzed, 5 were of the claimed strength or above, 6 were below strength, 3 were well below the claimed strength, and 8 possessed either none or extremely small amounts of active ingredient. Half of the analyzed samples were below 55% of the claimed strength. The active ingredient in the Khmer product could not be identified.

Products were sourced from government stores, Vietnam, Japan, Thailand, and Luxembourg. All of the pesticides claimed to be from the government stores were inactive, and the remaining "fakes" were contained in bottles possessing Vietnamese labels. Some Vietnamese products, however, were analyzed and found to have high concentrations of active ingredient.

The results of this study indicate that product regulation is necessary both for safety and quality control. This could be achieved by banning the importation of WHO category I pesticides and discouraging adulteration of products at the place of sale by imposing fines or other disincentives. ■